

Empowering Research Talent: Building R&I Talent Ecosystems to Advance Careers in Health Innovation

D8.2 Data Management Plan

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13	AP	Nando	UAB Nando
14	AP	ALIRA HEALTH SL	ALIRA HEALTH SL
15	AP	CasZyme	CasZyme

Legend = Role in the Project: **COO**– Coordinator // **BEN**– Beneficiary // **AE** – Affiliated Entity // **AP** – Associated Partner

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
EC	European Commission
WP	Work Package
T	Task
D	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the data management plan (DMP) for the BREATH project. It details the BREATH consortium's plan to manage the production, collection, and processing of its data and scientific publications, during and after the project. It is a living document that will be updated during the project and reviewed by the consortium at a minimum following the periodic evaluations of the project. Each project partner handling and bearing responsibility for data collected, stored, or used in BREATH will ensure compliance with the strategy outlined herein. This document follows EU guidelines for data management.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND

BREATH's Data Management Plan (DMP) (T8.5) contains information on the handling of research data during and after the end of the project. It indicates what data will be collected, processed, and/or generated; which methodology and standards will be applied; what – if any – data will be shared or made open access; and how data will be curated and preserved (including after the project's end). The plan will be updated throughout the project lifetime if significant changes arise (e.g., new data or changes in policies or in the consortium). As a minimum, the DMP will be updated before the end of the project (September 2028). The consortium will be guided by the findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) Guiding Principles for scientific data management. To facilitate data exchange and re-use, partners will use common, standardised file formats in a consistent manner.

1.2 STRUCTURE OF THE REPORT

This report follows the structure recommended in the European Commission's Horizon Europe Data Management Plan template of 1 April 2022¹.

Section 2 (data summary) presents an overview of research and personal data that will be collected, processed and generated in the project. These include data such as contact lists, deliverables, and scientific publications. Section 3 (fair data) explains how BREATH will meet the FAIR requirements, making data Findable (3.1), Accessible (3.2), Interoperable (3.3) and Reusable (3.4). Section 4 (allocation of resources) specifies the resources that will be used to guarantee good data management. Section 5 (data security) discusses the protection of personal data that is collected and processed in the context of the project. Section 6 (ethics) covers ethical aspects, while Section 7 (other issues) will cover any additional aspects not addressed in the previous sections, if applicable.

2. DATA SUMMARY

A general overview of the data collected in BREATH is presented in Table 1. Data summary. It covers data information such as types, formats, the expected size, origin, purpose of collection, data sharing and data utility for each of the Work Packages (WP). The information was gathered in collaboration with the consortium partners and will be updated throughout the project.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/temp-form/report/data-management-plan_he_en.docx

Table 1. Data summary

WP	Linked objective	Type	Formats	Size	Origin	Data sharing	Data utility
WP 1	Co-creating the Talent Ecosystem						
T1.1; T1.2; T1.3	Co-creating the Talent Eco-system	Work plan, internal notes	MSWord, Excel, PowerPoint, and PDF documents	<1GB	G	Internal use	Input for WP1 tasks
T1.1	Proof of the stakeholders involved in the Talent Ecosystem (Milestone 1)	List of key stakeholders for the Talent Ecosystem	PDF (D1.1)	<1GB	G	Open	European Commission
T1.1	To analyse the partners' motivations, needs, capacity and incentives	Audio, video and transcription of recordings of interviews	Audio and video files, Word, Excel, and PDF documents	<10GB	G	Internal use	Input for D1.1
T1.1		Survey responses	Word, Excel, and PDF documents. To make the spreadsheet data open, .csv will be used.	<1GB	G	Open	Input for D1.1; Sister projects; future Talent ecosystem projects;
T1.2	To design the governance framework and operating model within the Talent Eco-system	Regional co-creation workshops of the Talent Ecosystem results	Word, Excel, PowerPoint; MURAL/ MIRO online web tool with BIOCAT or Task partners licenses; PDF documents.	<7GB	G	Internal use	Input for D1.2
T1.2		F2F Co-creation workshop of the Partnership Agreements for HI results	Word, Excel, PowerPoint; MURAL/MIRO online web tool with BIOCAT or Task partners licenses; PDF documents.	<1GB	G	Internal use	Input for D1.2
T1.3	To define the activities of the Talent Eco-systems	Three online meetings with the Talent Ecosystem actors results	Word, Excel, Power-Point; MURAL/ MIRO online web tool with	<2GB	G	Internal use	Input for D1.3

WP	Linked objective	Type	Formats	Size	Origin	Data sharing	Data utility
			IA or Task partners licenses; PDF documents.				
T1.1; T1.2; T1.3	Co-creating the Talent Eco-system	Workshop Invitees'/ participants' contacts	Forms, Excel	<1GB	G	Internal use	Input for WP1 tasks
WP 2	Identifying career paths, related skills and training						
T2.1; T2.2; T2.3; T2.4	Identifying career paths, related skills and training	Work plan, internal notes	MSWord, Excel, PowerPoint, and PDF documents	<1GB	G	Internal use	N/A
T2.2	To engage non-academic stakeholders in the identification of skills mismatches and joint development of the career path and skills	Delphi study survey responses	Word, Excel, and PDF documents.	<1GB	G	Open	Input for D2.1; Sister projects; future Talent ecosystem projects; possible collaborations, (project) outreach activities
T2.1		Survey responses	Survey software (EU-Survey), Word, Excel, and PDF documents. To make the spreadsheet data open, .csv will be used.	<1GB	G	Open	
T2.3	To provide a comprehensive overview of the trans-versal training provided by the members of the consortium (Milestone 2)	Mapping of transversal training opportunities for R1 and R2 profiles	Word, Excel, and PDF documents. To make the spreadsheet data open, .csv will be used.	<1GB	G	Open	Input for D2.2; Sister projects; future Talent ecosystem projects; R1 and R2 researchers interested in training opportunities; training providers
T2.3	To co-develop training opportunities to address the skills mismatch and the training gaps identified	Internal notes for the co-design of the Capacity Building Program	Word, Excel, and PDF documents.	<1GB	G	Internal use	Input for D2.2
T2.4	To create resources to improve the career path	Dashboard	Public PowerBI dashboard on	<1GB	G	Open	Input for D2.3; Sister projects; future Talent

WP	Linked objective	Type	Formats	Size	Origin	Data sharing	Data utility
	guidance at universities		the project's website, .pbix				ecosystem projects; R1 and R2 researchers interested in training opportunities; training providers
T2.4		Feedback on the dashboard	Forms, Word, Excel, and PDF documents.	<1GB	G	Internal use	Input for D2.4
T2.1; T2.2; T2.3; T2.4	Identifying career paths, related skills and training	Workshop Invitees'/ participants' contacts	Forms, Excel	<1GB	G	Internal use	N/A
WP 3	Capacity building for career path guidance services						
T3.1; T3.2; T3.3	Capacity building for career path guidance	Work plan, internal notes	MSWord, Excel, PowerPoint, and PDF documents	<1GB	G	Internal use	N/A
T3.1	To develop a comprehensive understanding of existing career path guidance services in universities	Benchmark of career services at higher education institutions	Word, Excel, and PDF documents. To make the spreadsheet data open, .csv will be used.	<1GB	G	Open	Input for D3.1; Sister projects; future Talent ecosystem projects
T3.1	Identify best practices from non-academic actors.	Best practices in career guidance from non-academic actors	Word, Excel, and PDF documents. To make the spreadsheet data open, .csv will be used.	<10GB	G	Open	Input for D3.1; Sister projects; future Talent ecosystem projects
T3.2	To facilitate mutual learning and the exchange of best practices among universities and businesses aiming at career path guidance services.	Results of the online and F2F meetings with the career advisors	Word, Excel, and PDF documents.	<1GB	G	Internal use	Input for D3.2
T3.2	Proof of the establishment of the mutual	Names of the mutual	PDF (D3.2)	<1GB	G	Open	European Commission

WP	Linked objective	Type	Formats	Size	Origin	Data sharing	Data utility
	learning community (Milestone 3)	learning community					
T3.2; T3.3	Capacity building for career path guidance	Workshop Invitees'/ participants' contacts	Forms, Excel	<1GB	G	Internal use	N/A
WP 4	Piloting the BREATH Experience						
T4.1; T4.2; T4.3: T4.4	Capacity building for career path guidance	Work plan, internal notes	MSWord, Excel, PowerPoint, and PDF documents	<1GB	G	Internal use	N/A
T4.2; T4.3: T4.4	Piloting the BREATH experience	Workshop Invitees'/ participants' contacts	Forms, Excel	<1GB	G	Internal use	N/A
WP 5	Monitoring, evaluation and assessment						
T5.1; T 5.2; T5.3	Monitoring, Evaluation and Assessment	Work plan, internal notes	MSWord, Excel, PowerPoint, and PDF documents	<1GB	G	Internal use	N/A
T5.1	To design a methodology and framework to measure the progress, outcomes and impacts of the project.	F2F Co-creation workshop of the Monitoring & Evaluation Framework results	MSWord, Excel, PowerPoint, and PDF documents	<1GB	G	Internal use	Input for D5.1
T5.2	To monitor project performance and the impact of institutional changes on research career.	Monitoring reports	MSWord, Excel, PowerPoint, and PDF documents	<10GB	G	Internal use	Inputs for D5.2
T5.2	To monitor project performance and the impact of institutional changes on research career.	F2F Data Reflection meeting	MSWord, Excel, PowerPoint, and PDF documents, MIRO/ MURAL	<1GB	G	Internal use	Inputs for D5.2
T5.3	To evaluate the project activities, the outcomes achieved, the corresponding	Audio, video and transcription of recording of interviews	Audio and video files, Word, Excel, and PDF documents.	<10GB	G	Internal use	Inputs for D5.2

WP	Linked objective	Type	Formats	Size	Origin	Data sharing	Data utility
T5.3	institutional changes and their impact.	Virtual Validation Workshop with the SAB results		<1GB	G	Internal use	Inputs for D5.2
WP 6	Sustainability and policy recommendations						
T6.1; T6.2	Sustainability and policy recommendations	Work plan, internal notes	MSWord, Excel, PowerPoint, and PDF documents	<1GB	G	Internal use	N/A
T6.1	To elaborate policy recommendations with a view to providing meaningful advice on how to create attractive careers for ECR	Results of the three regional policy workshops in Catalonia, Flanders and Lithuania	MSWord, Excel, PowerPoint, and PDF documents	<1GB	G	Open	Inputs for D6.1 and D6.2
T6.2	To safeguard the sustainability of the institutional changes stimulated by the project and ensure the commitment of the stakeholders involved beyond the end of the grant.	Results of the three regional workshops	MSWord, Excel, PowerPoint, and PDF documents	<1GB	G	Open	Inputs for D6.3
WP 7	Communication, dissemination and legacy						
T7.3	To identify and nurture relationships with stakeholders	Stakeholder database	Word, Excel, PowerPoint, and PDF files	<1GB	G	Internal use	For the engagement of the Talent Ecosystem actors
T7.4	To develop a plan to exploit the project results and a roadmap for the long-term implementation of the resulting measures, including further uptake and upscaling	IPR internal workshop results	Word, Excel, PowerPoint, PDF files, MIIRO	<1GB	G	Internal use	Input for D7.4
WP 8	Project management and coordination						

WP	Linked objective	Type	Formats	Size	Origin	Data sharing	Data utility
T8.1	To drive and coordinate project progress, steering partners' efforts towards achieving objectives and milestones.	Contact details of consortium members	Excel	>1GB	G	Internal use	N/A

Notes: *Origin*: R – reuse; G – generate; *Data access*: O – Open; C – Closed, TBU – to be updated, N/A – not applicable

Project partners will generate outputs in the different tasks (Table 2) that will be managed and made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

Table 2. Overview of outputs to be published open access on Zenodo

Related tasks and responsible partner	Title of the output	DOI	Utility
T1.1 (BIOCAT)	Stakeholders' requirements and motivations to engage in the Talent Ecosystems (Dataset)	TBU	To support further research on Talent Ecosystems, and to inform policymakers and other key actors on key motivations and barriers.
T1.1 (BIOCAT)	Stakeholders' requirements and motivations to engage in the Talent Ecosystems (R — Document, report)	TBU	To provide evidence-based insights for the design and implementation of Talent Ecosystems, informing policymakers and key actors.
T1.2 (BIOCAT)	Partnership Agreements for HI (R — Document, report)	TBU	To serve as a reference model for the formalisation of stakeholder collaboration and commitments in Talent Ecosystems, enabling replication in other regions.
T1.3 (IA)	Pilot operation plans for the institutional changes of the Talent Ecosystem (R — Document, report)	TBU	To offer a structured and actionable roadmap that guides stakeholders in piloting institutional changes within the Talent Ecosystem.
T1.3 (IA)	Implementation of Institutional changes (R — Document, report)	TBU	To document and evaluate the execution of institutional changes, providing practical insights that support continuous improvement within the Talent Ecosystem.
T2.1 (BIOVIA) and T2.2 (KUL)	Career paths and relevant skills for PhD holders in Health Innovation (Dataset)	TBU	To provide evidence-based insights for development of trainings within project and ecosystem. To inform stakeholders on the skill gaps in the sector.
T2.2 (KUL)	Assessing competence needs for Early career researchers in different HI career paths (R — Document, report)	TBU	To provide evidence-based insights for the design and implementation of trainings within project and ecosystem. To inform stakeholders on the skill gaps in the sector

Related tasks and responsible partner	Title of the output	DOI	Utility
			and to which degree expert panels come to consensus on this.
T2.3 (UAB)	Database of transversal training opportunities for R1 and R2 profiles (Dataset)	TBU	To serve as inspiration for other institutions willing to provide training for R1 and R2 researchers aligned with the different competence frameworks and addressing the skills identified by the consortium as important.
T2.3 (UAB)	Capacity Building Programme for the career paths for HI ECR (R — Document, report)	TBU	To serve as inspiration for other institutions willing to improve/change their capacity building programmes
T2.4 (UAB)	Career Path Guidance Platform (DEC —Websites, patent filings, videos, etc)	TBU	To serve as inspiration for other institutions willing to make visible the training offer and the related skills, related to specific career paths for specific areas of knowledge and level of expertise.
T2.4 (UAB)	Career Path Guidance Platform final version (DEC —Websites, patent filings, videos, etc)	TBU	
T3.1 (KTU)	Database of career services offered by higher education institutions (Dataset)	TBU	To provide a structured overview of career services offered by higher education institutions, enabling stakeholders to understand, compare, and enhance researchers support systems.
T3.1 (KTU)	Database of best practices in career guidance from non-academic actors (Dataset)	TBU	To provide a structured collection of best practices in career guidance delivered by non-academic actors, enabling stakeholders to understand, compare, and apply effective approaches across diverse contexts.
T3.1 (KTU)	Landscape and good practices of researcher's career guidance (R — Document, report)	TBU	To provide a comprehensive overview of the landscape and good practices in researcher career guidance, enabling stakeholders to understand current approaches, identify effective models, and support evidence-based policy and institutional development.
T3.2 (KUL)	BREATH career guidance experience and roadmaps for implementation (R — Document, report)	TBU	This is useful for other institutions to learn from practices for embedding and accelerating these services at each university

Related tasks and responsible partner	Title of the output	DOI	Utility
T3.3 (KUL)	Piloting ECR Career Guidance and Training Programs within Universities (R — Document, report)	TBU	To serve as an inspiration for other institutions or initiatives on how to outline career guidance experience and implementation roadmaps.
T4.1 (UAB)	Pilot Operation Plans for the implementation of the BREATH Experience (R — Document, report)	TBU	Other initiatives or projects wanting to improve, in a coherent manner, career guidance and training.
T4.2 and T4.3 (KTU)	Piloting ECR Career Guidance and Training Programs within Universities (R — Document, report)	TBU	To present the piloting of early-career researcher (ECR) career guidance and training programs within universities, enabling stakeholders to assess implementation approaches, evaluate effectiveness, and support evidence-based development of career support initiatives.
T5.1 (UAB)	BREATH Monitoring and Evaluation Framework (R — Document, report)	TBU	Useful for other Talent Ecosystems wanting to evaluate their impact. The ME framework can be adapted to any specificities of other projects.
T5.2 and T5.3 (UAB)	Evaluation of BREATH's Talent Ecosystems' performance and impact (R — Document, report)	TBU	Useful for other Talent Ecosystems to see the successes and limitations of such a collaboration
T6.1 (AGAUR)	1 st Policy brief (R — Document, report)	TBU	Useful for informing policymakers and stakeholders across regions and other EU initiatives, providing transferable, evidence-based guidance that can be adapted to different policy contexts to improve career opportunities for early-career researchers.
T6.1 (AGAUR)	2 nd Policy brief (R — Document, report)	TBU	
T6.2 (BIOCAT)	Sustainability road map for the Talent Ecosystem	TBU	Useful for other Talent Ecosystems and institutions as a replicable model to design and implement sustainability action plans, which can be adapted to local contexts to ensure long-term institutional change and stakeholder commitment beyond project funding.
T7.3 (WeDo)	Plan for stakeholder engagement (R — Document, report)	TBU	Useful for other EC funded projects that have a high degree of interaction with the stakeholders of their ecosystems for project implementation
T8.5 (UAB)	Data Management Plan (R — Document, report)	TBU	Other EU-funded projects can use the same structure and adapt the content to the specific project.

Related tasks and responsible partner	Title of the output	DOI	Utility
T8.5 (UAB)	Final Data Management Plan (R — Document, report)	TBU	Useful for other EU-funded projects (and also funded by other sources) to consider specific aspects of their Data Management Plans.

Note: DOIs of the outputs will be updated in D8.3 Final Data Management Plan.

3. FAIR DATA

3.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

Every new record (such as deliverables and datasets) previously settled to be published and/or disseminated as an open format will be assigned a DOI in Zenodo. Metadata will include the DOI of its concerned dataset, material or output.

The Zenodo principles will be followed to provide rich metadata to allow discovery, considering that Zenodo’s metadata complies with the DataCite’s Metadata Schema minimum and recommended terms, and adds some items to consider².

A set of keywords have been selected for consistency and to optimise the discoverability and re-usage of the (meta)data: Talent Ecosystem; Early Career Researchers; Career Paths; Research Careers; Talent Development; Health Innovation.

Metadata will be made openly available under CC0 (Creative Commons Zero v1.0 Universal in Zenodo) to maximise re-use and harvesting. Zenodo exposes records for harvesting via OAI-PMH, and DOIs are registered and indexed by DataCite, enabling broad discovery and citation tracking. Open content in Zenodo is harvestable by third parties and integrated into OpenAIRE workflows, ensuring inclusion in European discovery ecosystems and project reporting.

Table 3. Metadata to be provided about each record

Information	Description
Digital Object Identifier (M)	If the author already has a DOI for the specific upload, it will be specified. If not, Zenodo will provide one.
Resource type (M)	The most relevant resource types for this project will be “Dataset” and “Project deliverable”.
Title (M)	Title of the output

² <https://about.zenodo.org/principles/>
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Information	Description
Publication date	Date of the first publication
Authors/Creators (M)	Members of the responsible institution(s) of the output involved in its elaboration. For example, in the case of D2.1, both BIOVIA and KUL members should be listed as authors. With ORCID if applicable.
Description (M)	Clear and concise description of the output (dataset, project deliverable, etc.) It can cover its objective, contents, type and original source of the data, method of collection, etc.
License (M)	For peer-reviewed journal articles, Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International is required. For metadata, Creative Commons Zero v1.0 Universal is required. For the rest of outputs, the recommended license to use is Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, as open as possible, as closed as necessary.
Copyright (M)	Adapted to the chosen license.
Contributor(s) (R)	People who made active contributions to the elaboration of the output.
Keywords and subjects (MA)	Keywords that will help to tag, find and index the output. These keywords should be included in every output: Talent Ecosystem; Early Career Researchers; Career Paths; Research Careers; Talent Development; Health Innovation. Other specific keywords can be added, if applicable, considering the information provided in Table 2. Key messages and communicational objectives of the internal D7.2 Communication and dissemination plan and tools
Languages (R)	English is the default language.
Date (M)	Date on which the resource was made available
Publisher (M)	By default, it will be Zenodo. It should be modified if applicable.
Awards/Grants (M)	101217137 European Commission (BE)
Related works (MA)	In the case of Project deliverables or publications with datasets, the corresponding dataset should be added as related work with the Relation "Is supplemented by". In the case of Datasets, the corresponding Project deliverable or Publication should be added with the Relation "Is supplement to", and the corresponding metadata should be added with the Relation "Has metadata". In the case of the

Information	Description
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Metadata, the corresponding Dataset should be added with the Relation “Is Metadata for”.

Note: The format is automatically detected by Zenodo, and any user can use the filter “File type”.

3.2 MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE

Repository

The data will be deposited in a trusted repository, which is Zenodo, in the EU-project community [BREATH project: Empowering Research Talent: Building R&I Talent Ecosystems to Advance Careers in Health Innovation](#), a subcommunity of [EU Open Research Repository](#).

Figure 1. BREATH community in Zenodo

Deposits undergo metadata checks and file-format checks to encourage open/scientific formats—helping the project members to meet Horizon Europe requirements. The EU Open Research Repository provides higher quotas and supports versioning with stable DOIs. We will interlink outputs (deliverables, datasets, publications) using DataCite relation types via Zenodo’s “Related identifiers” (e.g., IsSupplementedBy, IsSupplementTo, HasMetadata/IsMetadataFor), as specified in Table 3.

Upon publication, Zenodo automatically registers a DOI for each record via DataCite. Each DOI resolves to a stable landing page (record) with rich metadata and the associated files, ensuring persistent, citable access to the digital object; Zenodo also supports versioned DOIs with a concept DOI for the whole record family.

Data

BREATH consortium partners will make datasets and other outputs accessible to third parties for reuse. All data gathered within the BREATH project and planned to be published in a data repository will be anonymised. Non-personal data which has been gathered and used in research reports, project deliverables and articles will be made open access (OA) for reuse by the consortium partners. Personal data collected within the BREATH project will be processed exclusively for the purposes defined in the project. Personal data will not be disseminated.

Where datasets are published in repositories (e.g., Zenodo), they will be anonymised to prevent re-identification, and shared only where this is compatible with the original purpose of data collection.

Open datasets will be downloadable over standard HTTPS from Zenodo record landing pages, and programmatically accessible via Zenodo's REST API (for files and records). No proprietary client is required.

If the project members identify, during the implementation of the project, that certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions, this Data Management Plan will be updated accordingly.

Metadata

Metadata will be publicly accessible and licensed under the public domain (Creative Commons - CC0), meaning that no authorization will be necessary to retrieve it, as specified in Table 3.

Data and metadata will be retained for the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN. Metadata is stored in database servers at CERN, which is separate from the data itself.

The spreadsheet data will be accessible and readable, as it will be shared in .csv, a non-proprietary format.

3.3 MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

Data formats listed in Table 1 will be revised and converted to non-proprietary formats before publication, such as .csv for tabular or spreadsheet data. The relation between resources can be made through the "Relation" element in the metadata. While uploading data and outputs to the repository, consistent keywords will be used. Descriptions of the datasets and metadata are in English to increase their discoverability and accessibility.

In terms of interoperable metadata, Zenodo uses JSON Schema as an internal representation of metadata and offers export to other popular formats such as Dublin Core or MARCXML.

3.4 INCREASE DATA RE-USE

To validate data analysis and facilitate data reuse, shared and accessible data is provided with README files with information on the investigators, methodology and access to files to explain the content, folder and/or file. An adapted version the README file template provided by UAB³ is available in the BREATH SharePoint for the consortium partners.

In principle, the data, materials, and outputs generated within the BREATH project can be of interest to any researcher in academia, public and private organisations; employers of researchers in the public and private sectors; funders of research and researchers in the

³ https://ddd.uab.cat/pub/guibib/226740/README_a2024iENG.txt
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public and private sector; and policy-makers concerned with policies related to the European Charter for Researchers, in particular to Pillar 4 on “Research careers and talent development”. In addition, it can also be of interest to the members of the other nine sister projects of the Talent Ecosystems call, in addition to the members of the new Talent Ecosystem call coming up in 2027.

Data will be labelled with Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 licence to maximise its reusability of all data deposited in Zenodo. This licence places the copyright in the public domain, so that others may freely build upon, enhance, and reuse the works.

The consortium partners have the goal to produce reliable data. The data quality assurance process is as follows:

1. Data collection and data analysis

Measures taken include checking the authenticity of secondary material and systematically note its sources; using standardised methods and protocols for data collection (such as interviews, surveys and workshops’ results); providing good quality of collected data; curating data systematically so that data not allowed by consent or not relevant for the deliverable or publication is excluded from analysis.

2. Digitalisation and data entry

Measures taken include using of templates for documentation and creating a logical folder structure to organise data in files.

3. Data checking

Measures taken include double-checking of observations or responses; checking data completeness; correcting errors made during transcription; cross-check notes.

4. Data authenticity

Measures taken include keeping and maintaining original data files, keeping information of sources of data, and keeping history of data analysis files.

The following guidelines should be applied for naming and versioning the outputs: [date]_[name-of-the-file]_[version].[format], for example:

20260531_survey-on-career-paths_v1.csv

If the outputs evolve during the implementation of the project, it is encouraged to upload the different versions of it, under the same master DOI.

4. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

All partners of BREATH are responsible for the implementation of FAIR practices when collecting and storing data. The coordinator can be approached if assistance is needed.

Specifically, it is important that enough time is considered in the research process to ensure the quality of the data, to prepare transcripts, to pseudonymise them when needed, to document the data and to format files into sustainable formats. No extra costs are foreseen to occur to cover these activities. The costs for data storage can be found in Table 4 below.

The implementation of best Data Management practices and FAIR principles is supported by professional expertise at the Library Services, privacy officers the Ethics Committee and legal advisors available through the project coordinator UAB.

5. DATA SECURITY

When collecting personal data, principles of anonymisation and pseudo-anonymisation will be followed in order to protect the privacy of participants. The project partners are also aware of the responsibility to anonymise data before depositing it to Zenodo.

As indicated in Table 4 below, access to different storage tools is controlled by the members of the Coordination team, UAB. As part of the project management strategy, an overview of the single consortium members to the Teams and SharePoint of the project is maintained and regularly updated.

The specifics of the chosen data storage solutions for the project can be found in Table 4.

Table 4. Storage solutions

Storage solution	Microsoft 365 SharePoint	Zenodo
Stored data	Documentation of the project, administrative data	Data, metadata, project outputs
Access management	Coordinator	Coordinator (accepts submissions)
Access rights	All consortium members, single folders accessible by selection of consortium	Public (where applicable; access may be restricted or embargoed in line with ethical, legal, or contractual constraints)
Preservation period	Short-term: 5 years after the end of the project.	Long term: Lifetime of the repository
Backup and security measures	Password-protected and securely stored on the project's cloud-based drive (Microsoft 365 SharePoint, managed by the project coordinator) and in the	Security specification, (Meta)data are backed up during the night and replicated into multiple copies in the online system

Storage solution	Microsoft 365 SharePoint	Zenodo
	<p>internal password-protected drive of task partners.</p> <p>According to Microsoft, metadata backups are kept for 14 days and can be restored to any point in time within a five-minute window.</p> <p>The consortium can use Version history to roll back, and the recycle bin or site collection recycle bin to restore. If an item is removed from the site collection recycle bin, the project members can call support within 14 days to access a backup⁴.</p>	
Costs	UAB general Microsoft 365 license	Free of charge

If the partners storage any provisional data in their own repository (outside of the BREATH Sharepoint), they will do so in compliance with applicable GDPR and national legislations.

6. ETHICS

The BREATH project has been approved by the Ethics Committee at UAB.

Informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation will be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data.

7. OTHER ISSUES

The BREATH project will not use other procedures for data management.

⁴ <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/sharepoint/safeguarding-your-data> [101217137] [BREATH] [Deliverable 8.2]